

Simone Signaroli

A chancellor's desk

Valle Camonica in the XVIIth Century

A paper presented at Birkbeck, University of London,
workshop *Chanceries in the territories:*
Localities, Centres, Peripheries (21 march 2013)

Servizio Archivistico Comprensoriale di Valle Camonica

2013

Servizio Archivistico
Comprensoriale
di Valle Camonica

European
Research
Council

Simone Signaroli

A chancellor's desk. Valle Camonica in the XVIIth Century

A paper presented at Birkbeck, University of London, workshop *Chanceries in the territories: Localities, Centres, Peripheries* (21 march 2013).

AR.C.H.I.ves Project. A comparative history of archives in late medieval and early modern Italy

Funded by the European Research Council

www.bbk.ac.uk/history/archives/

Pubblicazioni del Servizio Archivistico Comprensoriale di Valle Camonica - ISSN 2281-8944

www.cmvallecamonica.bs.it/pagine/archivi

Breno 2013

Copyright of the author

Simone Signaroli

A chancellor's desk Valle Camonica in the XVIIth Century

1. Introduction

In the present essay,¹ I'll try to illustrate how many documents, ancient and modern, lay on a chancellor's desk in the Seventeenth Century, when public officials and politicians were well acquainted with history, as they are nowadays with economics (or would have to be). In short, we must imagine a desk like that of the antiquary in Sir Walter Scott's novel: «A large, old-fashioned oaken table was covered with a profusion of papers, parchments, books...» and so on (Scott's *Antiquary*, ch. III).

And because I read this paper in London, I cannot but remember an eminent Englishman, scholar, collector and acute politician in the early Seventeenth Century: Robert Bruce Cotton. This one may offer a good portrait of that kind of student, involved in political affairs: he collected and studied ancient charters (Magna Carta above all), manuscripts (Lindisfarne Gospel, Beowulf, Matthew Paris' works) and Roman inscribed stones, and meanwhile managed Parliament and Crown affairs. Today, it is certainly a hard job to meet with such a man in the Parliament; it is, as I said, more easy to find a fine economist.

But, considering Seventeenth-Century Europe, it will be made apparent that Sir Robert was not alone. In fact, the master of Cotton's biographers, Kevin Sharpe, truly wrote that in the early Seventeenth Century «men studied history primarily for its use and application for contemporary affairs rather than, as we still often wish, to advance historical understanding».² Among Cotton's fellows in historical studies, my paper does not look at most obvious names, as it may be the case of William Camden in England, Hugo Grotius in the Netherlands, or Nicolas Fabri de Peiresc in France. Rather, I intend to turn to the local chanceries of the Venetian Republic, where officials kept the archives of communes that entered the Republic during XIVth to XVth Centuries.

2. The Commune of Valle Camonica

Studies on that chanceries and archives generally concern communes, city-states or territorial states. Such is the case of Venice, analysed by Filippo De Vivo,³ or Padua and other cities, towns and communities in the Venetian Republic.⁴

Among them, we have to number Valle Camonica: a valley in the central-Italian Alps, that presents us with a somewhat Scottish-like landscape. Valle Camonica, in the Middle Ages and early modern era, is sometimes described as a federative union of

rural communes.⁵ In part it may be true: representatives of each commune of the valley composed a general council, that ruled the region.

But it is a fact that in 1164 emperor Frederic I had addressed *homines et milites Vallis Camonicae* as a commune as a whole, in a charter by means of which he approved the existence of the commune, stating its independence from any other political power.

Then, in 1311, Valcamonica presented itself to Henry VII as a unique commune; on that occasion, when the king confirmed the antique privilege by his predecessor Frederic, one *procurator et syndicus*, Cunradus de Ydulo, was acting for the commune. Lastly, we know that Henry VII appointed Iohannes de Crema *vicarius* in Valcamonica in the same 1311.

So, we can perhaps say that Valle Camonica was a territorial commune, as Brescia, Milan or Padua were municipal communes. It follows that, if municipal communes were city-states, Valle Camonica was somewhat a valley-state, if I may.⁶

Indeed in 1427-28, when Valle Camonica entered the Republic of Venice, this city did not negotiate with the duke of Milan or the Commune of Brescia -the influence of both reached the valley-,⁷ but with Valle Camonica and its parliament, as some decrees of the Senate in Venice attest.⁸ And the ducal letter that confirmed the annexation of the valley to the republic was addressed to the Commune of Valle Camonica itself (on the 1st July 1428).⁹

Since that date to 1440, the valley had direct contact with Venice: every year in the city a patrician was appointed rector to the Commune of Valle Camonica, and moved to its capital town, Breno. According to the Statute, he swore allegiance to the valley in Saint Anthony church and lodged in a public building (next to the church, at right hand), the *Palatium Breni*. This building, into which the local council of representatives (or parliament) met, kept the archive and hosted chancellors' rooms.

In 1440 Venetian government put Valle Camonica into Brescia district. This decision implied a downgrade for the valley, and caused a long-term political reaction by the Commune, the officials of which made use of archive documents and antiquarian scholarship in order to assert its rights: privileges, properties, institutional "liberties" and the same existence of the Commune and its Statute of laws were in fact founded on medieval charters.

3. The journey of a chancellor: from Valle Camonica to Venice

It is the case of Bernardino Ronchi, chancellor since 1583 to 1616 and friend of the antiquary Ottavio Rossi, student of the history of Brescia and Valle Camonica. Contemporaneous with Robert Cotton, Bernardino was either son and father of chancellors: respectively Girolamo (chancellor since 1532 to about 1576) and Paolo (1618-1625).

Ronchi family was deeply involved in local political life. Saint Anthony church itself

belonged to the town of Breno by means of an ancient legacy disposed by one of Bernardino's ancestors, Iohannes Maro de Runchis (second half of the XIVth Century).¹⁰

Communes had a republican shape of government. So, communal aristocracy was usually composed by merchants and notaries that inhabited city-centres. That is true also in post-medieval, post-communal republics of the early modern era. Walter Scott in his novel *The Fortunes of Nigel*, set in the early XVIIth Century, very well summarized this condition in a few words, pronounced by the character of Lady Hermione, daughter of a merchant from Genoa (a republic, as Venice was): «My father was a merchant, but he was of a city whose merchants are princes» (Scott's *The Fortunes of Nigel*, vol. II, ch. II).

According to republican rules, the council of representatives was the core of local government, and it was regarded as if it embodied the sovereignty of the State: for instance the Senate of Venice was named «augustissimus» by Dutch scholar Ioannes Meursius in a treaty on the ancient parliament of Athens.¹¹

So, in Valle Camonica, as elsewhere, political and economic power was managed by the families that expressed representatives, i.e. such men as lairds, landowners, merchants, barristers and notaries, usually members of a local gentry.

The general council, composed by over 100 people, met only three times in a year, while select councils of a few members usually worked every week on several matters. Members of the parliament, who were in charge for one year, were elected by a central commission, that appointed representatives of each rural commune (probably proposed by local councils). In the last meeting of the year, between 25 and 31 december, the general council chose a *sindicus generalis*, i.e. a “prime minister”, and the chancellor.¹²

Frequently (if not always) notaries were appointed chancellors, because of their power to give force of law to any writing.¹³ Chancellors were in fact charged with keeping the archive of the commune, with writing public letters, with making certified copies taken from original documents. To say it in a nutshell: what notaries did in private, chancellors did in public. Such was the case, for instance, of Sicco Polenton in Padua (appointed chancellor in about 1420).¹⁴ But we must remember that also the most ancient chronicler of the same city, Rolandinus (XIIIth Century), had been a notary involved in public affairs.

Furthermore, the office of chancellor was a long-term position. To well manage an archive, we need experience and knowledge: in other words, an old chancellor is better than a new official, elected every year, because he simply knows where documents lie. For instance, we know that in Brescia, between XVth and XVIth Centuries, chancellors' appointments ended with the officials' death.

In Valle Camonica we can distinguish an early period (1492 to 1501), during which the elected chancellor was in charge for only one year (or for a few years), and a second step, in the XVIth to XVIIIth Centuries, when chancellors reached the long-term appointment, that was common to other communes.

So, it is not surprising that, since the half of the XVIth Century to the early Seventeenth, Ronchi family was capable to hold the office for three generations.

This dynasty started with Bernardino's father, Girolamo. When this one was appointed chancellor, Valle Camonica was filing a law suit against the city of Brescia, concerning what crimes and civil proceedings were within the valley's sphere of competence. Girolamo rushed to Venice and obtained a ruling letter by the Senate, that was favourable to the Commune of Valle Camonica.¹⁵

As frequently happened, the sentence did not end the case, that re-entered the scene in the early Seventeenth Century, when the Captain of Brescia tried to put within his jurisdiction every military case. This implied, of course, the moving of political power, but also of some economic gain to notaries-in-the-city from notaries-in-the-valley.

In fact, defending itself and its rights, the Commune of Valle Camonica defended also these economic interests, that were the interests of the families that ruled the valley and its institutions.

So, in 1604 Bernardino Ronchi wrote a long speech in defense of the autonomy of the valley, and read it before the Collegio in the Ducal Palace of Venice.¹⁶ What is of interest to us, is that he made use of both medieval documents and some elements of natural right in order to argue his own point of view.

I propose here a translation of the beginning of his speech:

Valcamonica: natively secluded by site, being surrounded by mountains and Iseo lake (or Sebinus), that is 15 miles long and divides Brescia and Bergamo districts, and Valcamonica, and by imperial privileges in 1164, confirmed in 1311, and by other acts by dukes and princes of Milan, Brescia and Valcamonica in 1339, 1349, 1365, 1384 and 1420, and lastly by the Most Serene Dominion of Venice in first acquisition, on the 1st July 1428, confirmed in 1453 and 1517, separated from the cities of Brescia and Bergamo and their districts, so that their rectors have not to interfere in its affairs, as other cities, near and far, have not to do.¹⁷

The very second word of the text was not written by chance. «Natively», in fact, implied a use of natural rights: if anyone would like to unite Brescia and Valcamonica, he act «against Nature and God», Bernardino seems to say. The speech, in another paragraph, is more explicit:

Our Lord God, and the princes in the world, and Nature itself imposed separate jurisdictions; and so, your devoted valley does not expect that its Most Serene Highness the Prince cut off this right.¹⁸

If I may, Bernardino was a distant colleague of Hugo Grotius. And, as Hugo Grotius did in his treaty *De antiquitate Reipublicae Batavae* (*The antiquity of the Batavian Republic*), he made also use of medieval and early modern documents. In fact, he deeply knew the archive of the commune, and truly understood its history. The «imperial privilege in 1164, confirmed in 1311» is the charter by Frederic I, confirmed by Henry VII, of which I wrote in the second paragraph. It was kept in the archive of the Commune and on its back we can still read the ancient shelf-mark: «Filza prima, n° 3» (File 1, number 3: now Breno, Museo Camuno, Raccolta Putelli, Pergamena 602).

But Bernardino, during his appointment, was able to give us more informations on

conservation policies of the archive. In fact, he put together several copies of documents in a *dossier*, of which he possibly made use to compose his speech: the resulting file was named *Institutio regiminis Vallis Camonicae (Constitution of the government of Valle Camonica)*.¹⁹ In this file, the charter by Frederic I and Henry VII is stated to be a transcription of an intermediate copy in a register, dating possibly to the XVth Century.

So, we know that documents, which were considered particularly significant in the history of the valley, were copied each time a case required them. And it is clear that we need to know the history of that archive, and the contents of the chancellor's desk, if we want to understand his political action.

4. The chancellor's desk: antiquarian scholarship and archival policies

In 1663 Alberto Isonni, chancellor since 1637 to 1674, put in order some documents in the archive of the chancery. His work was concluded by Luca Cattaneo early in the XVIIIth Century, and it is preserved in a small register, *Inventario e repertorio delle scritture e raggioni reposte nell'armario novo della Cancellaria, radunate insieme da me Alberto Isonni cancellaro (Inventory and list of writings and rights kept in the new cabinet of the Chancery, put together by me, Alberto Isonni chancellor)*.²⁰

The inventory describes the content of a few cabinets: one of these is generically named as «new», the others are respectively numbered as 6, 8 and nine. So, we can argue that, between 1663 and about 1700 the archive of the commune was kept in 9 or 10 cabinets, and some chests, also listed by the inventory.

This information is useful to understand how much the archive had grown since 1433, when a chapter of the Statute established for the first time the institute, which was represented by only one cabinet with three shelves:

Furthermore, it is stated that, since this year, a public archive (or cabinet) must be established in this valley, with three shelves and three locks and keys, so that no one can open it with less than all three keys.²¹

According to the inventory, documents were collected in packs and files, as usual in the archives of early modern institutions. The document by chancellors Isonni and Cattaneo is a good guide to reconstruct the original order and the amount of the archive when this was intact, before the documents partly dispersed, and partly were inherited by the town of Breno, in 1797-1800, when the Commune of Valle Camonica was suppressed and the Republic of Venice ended its long history.

For instance, we have today only twelve registers, that preserve council records for the years 1492-1509, 1512-1516, 1567-1568, 1574-1576, 1586-1588, 1600-1602, 1611-1613, 1626-1628, 1666-1668, 1731-1735, 1784-1796; while the ancient inventory reports a complete list since 1536 to 1700.²² These registers are collected in one page of the inventory: so, we can suppose they were considered a single series, somehow separate from the rest of the archive.

Furthermore, we can ask the inventory what books and documents chancellors used to keep in their own desk:

In the first drawer below the chancellor's desk: the book on the history of Valle Camonica by Pietro Paolo Ormanico, printed;²³ the book on the history of Valle Camonica by reverend father Gregorio, reformed Franciscan friar;²⁴ and a small pack of ducal letters concerning various matters.

It may seem the inventory of Gulliver's pockets, edited by notaries in Lilliput. But it distinctly indicates that in Valle Camonica antiquarian scholarship was close to political action at the end of the Seventeenth Century, as it had been a century before, so that books on the history of the valley were kept together with contemporary documents.

In fact, as Bernardino Ronchi did, Alberto Isonni too was in some connection with historians and antiquaries: we know that he sent some informations on Roman inscribed stones to the antiquary Pietro Paolo Ormanico, who made use of them in his book, a copy of which reached the chancellor's desk. And the son of Alberto, vice-chancellor Antonio Isonni, allowed the historian Gregorio di Valcamonica to publish several documents, taken from the chancery, in his treaty on the antiquities of the valley, printed in Venice in 1698, that also was kept in the drawer described in the inventory.

5. Last impressions: to conclude

Officials like Bernardino Ronchi and Antonio Isonni communicated the knowledge of several medieval latin documents, that lay in a public archive, which was not publicly accessible: as many institutional archives, it was not open but to local professionals and politicians. We know, for instance, that in Brescia in 1628 Domenico Ruzzini, Venetian rector and representative of the State, had to ask the city council the license of studying a medieval register in the chancery: in fact, the archive was approachable only by officials of the commune itself.²⁵

However, in 1698, as we have seen, thanks to Antonio Isonni some charters and registers reached a wide-known antiquarian book. But it is Bernardino Ronchi's speech to give us the most interesting case.

We must imagine a chancellor travelling from an Alpine valley to the sea, in order to negotiate with powerful senators in Venice, gathered in the Collegio. To them he talk about a document produced by Henry VII in 1311. It happened in 1604, when a senator like Domenico Molino (himself a scholar and a citizen of the Republic of Letters) was taking his first steps in the political life in Venice. Afterwards, Domenico Molino affirmed himself as privileged correspondent with such scholars as Gerardus Ioannes Vossius and Isaac Casaubon. He believed that history is a necessary guide to any politician. For this purpose, he asked some students to publish the first edition of Albertino Mussato's historical works: among the others, also *De gestis Henrici VII Caesaris* (*On emperor Henry VII's undertakings*). That emperor, in his opinion, had been «an eminent politician, who moderated world's passions with a singularly acute civil wisdom».²⁶

As far as I know, in Domenico Molino's letters the archive of Valle Camonica never appears, and we cannot know whether Molino himself had any notice of it. But, of course, it could have happened.²⁷ So, the archive of Valle Camonica and its charters offer elements to our understanding of textual traditions, scholarly investigations and political action in the early modern Europe, as a letter by Casaubon does, or Cotton's copy of the Magna Carta, or any edition printed in Venice or Leiden. These ones emerge in surface, while the Alpine archive plays its role more secretly.

None of them must be overlooked, in no way.

Notes

¹ The occasion to write this article was offered by Filippo De Vivo, who invited me to present my researches on Valle Camonica in the XVIIth Century in a workshop (Birkbeck, University of London, 21 march 2013). This study is founded on some articles in Italian language, but it wants to offer a new perspective on the matter to english-speaking students: S. Signaroli, *Per una storia archivistica della cancelleria della Comunità di Valle Camonica in epoca veneta*, «Archivi», 7/2 (2012), pp. 69-80 (subsequently in the Pubblicazioni del Servizio Archivistico Comprensoriale di Valle Camonica, 2: <www.cmvallecamonica.bs.it/pagine/archivi/pubblicazioni>); Id., *La Valle Camonica nella scienza antiquaria del primo Seicento*, «Aevum», 86 (2012), pp. 1071-110. I am grateful to prof. De Vivo and to all workshop participants, as well as to my colleagues of the Servizio Archivistico Comprensoriale di Valle Camonica and il leggìo s.c.s. I thank Fabrizio Pagnoni and Enrico Valseriati, who read a first draft of this paper.

² K. Sharpe, *Introduction: rewriting Sir Robert Cotton*, in *Sir Robert Cotton as Collector. Essays on an Early Stuart Courtier and his Legacy*, ed. by C.J. Wright, London 1997, 1-39: 13.

³ F. De Vivo, *Ordering the archive in early modern Venice (1400-1650)*, «Archival Science», 10/3 (2010), pp. 234-48.

⁴ A general look: G.M. Varanini, *Public written records*, in *The Italian Renaissance State*, ed. by A. Gamberini and I. Lazzarini, Cambridge 2012, pp. 385-405. For cities and communities in the Terraferma, e.g. Padua: G. Bonfiglio Dosio, *L'amministrazione del territorio durante la Repubblica veneta (1405-1797): gli archivi dei rettori*, Padova 1996; Ead., *La politica archivistica del Comune di Padova dal XIII al XIX secolo, con l'inventario analitico del fondo "Costituzione e ordinamento dell'archivio"*, con un saggio di A. Desolei, Roma 2002. Sacile: *La storia ritrovata (1411-1797). Frammenti di vita sacilese tratti da documenti restaurati degli archivi storici comunale e parrocchiale*, ed. by N. Roman, Sacile 1993. Rovigo: G. Bonfiglio Dosio, C. Covizzi, C. Tognon, *L'amministrazione del territorio sotto la Repubblica di Venezia: gli archivi delle comunità e dei rettori*, Rovigo 2001. Valle Camonica: M. Della Misericordia, *Mappe di carte. Le scritture e gli archivi delle comunità rurali della montagna lombarda nel basso medioevo*, in *Archivi e comunità tra medioevo ed età moderna*, ed. by A. Bartoli Langeli, A. Giorgi e S. Moscadelli, Trento 2009. Archival studies, of course, must be read in a wider, historical view: so, it will be useful to put here a brief list of texts on Venice and its possessions in Northern Italy. On political and jurisdictional institutions in the Venetian Republic: *Stato società e giustizia nella Repubblica Veneta (sec. XV-XVIII)*, 2 voll., a cura di G. Cozzi, Roma 1980-1985. On local communities and feudal rights: S. Zamperetti, *I piccoli principi. Signorie locali, feudi e comunità soggette nello Stato*

regionale veneto dall'espansione territoriale ai primi decenni del '600, Venezia 1991; G.M. Varanini, *Comuni cittadini e stato regionale. Ricerche sulla Terraferma veneta nel Quattrocento*, Verona 1992; M. Knapton, *Venice and the Terraferma*, in *The Italian Renaissance State*, pp. 132-55.

⁵ M. Della Misericordia, *I nodi della rete. Paesaggio, società e istituzioni a Dalegno e in Valcamonica nel tardo medioevo*, in *La magnifica comunità di Dalegno. Dalle origini all'età napoleonica*, ed. by E. Bressan, Breno 2009, pp. 191-94. Id., *Mappe di carte*, pp. 201-4.

⁶ My words are intended to provoke discussion on this point, rather than conclude it. See Ph. Jones, *The Italian City-State. From Commune to Signoria*, Oxford 1997, p. 71: «urban territoria began to subdivide into lesser, rural counties (as of Lecco, Lomello, Sabbioneta etc.), into purely seigneurial districts under various counts and domini, or into subsidiary territoria, some in turn later designated 'counties', but a good number formed of regions (the Valtellina, Valcamonica, Frignano etc.) entirely dissociated, perhaps ever since antiquity, from any *civitas*». For a further, wide and comparative context: T. Scott, *The City-State in Europe (1000-1600). Hinterland, Territory, Region*, Oxford 2012.

⁷ For Milan and Valle Camonica in the early XVth Century see F. Pagnoni, *1420 I Visconti e la Valcamonica*, Breno 2012.

⁸ R. Putelli, *Intorno al castello di Breno*, Breno 1915, pp. 290-94. Documents: Venice, Archivio di Stato, *Senato Secreta*, reg. 10, f. 105v.

⁹ Now Breno, Museo Camuno, pergamena 608, ducal letter by Francesco Foscari (1st July 1428).

¹⁰ O. Franzoni, *Chiesa di Sant'Antonio Abate. Storia*, in *Arte in Val Camonica. Monumenti e opere*, V, ed. by B. Passamani, Breno 2004, p. 123.

¹¹ I. Meursii *Areopagus. Sive, De Senatu areopagitico liber singularis*, Lugduni Batavorum 1624, c. *2r: «Serenissimo Venetiarum Duci et Senatui Augustissimo Ioannes Meursius dedico consecroque».

¹² *Statuta Vallis Camonicae*, Brescia 1624, ch. 377, p. 154. For a first look on the *sindicatus* in early-modern Italy: G. Castelnuovo, *Offices and officials*, in *The Italian Renaissance State*, pp. 380-81.

¹³ For Alpine communities, in which archives of communes, communities and federations of communes were kept by notaries: Varanini, *Public written records*, p. 403.

¹⁴ Bonfiglio Dosio, *La politica archivistica*, p. 18.

¹⁵ D. Montanari, *Quelle terre di là dal Mincio*, Brescia 2004, pp. 170-72.

¹⁶ The speech is preserved in a couple of manuscripts: Breno, Museo Camuno, Raccolta Putelli, b. 19, fasc. 2 and b. 114, fasc. 3.1. An edition of the text is provided by S. Signaroli, *Tradizione e ius naturae in difesa dell'autonomia di Valle Camonica nella prima età moderna*, in *Naturalmente divisi. Storia e autonomia della antiche comunità alpine*, ed. by Luca Giarelli, 2013.

¹⁷ «Valcamonica: nativamente separata così per sito, essendo essa da monti e lago Sebino detto d'Iseo, lungo 15 miglia et più, che divide il Bresciano, il Bergamasco et Valcamonica, torniata da per sé, come per privilegi imperiali del 1164, confirmati del 1311 et d'altri duchi prencipi de Milano et Brescia et Valcamonica del 1339, 1349, 1365, 1384 et 1420, et del Serenissimo Dominio di Venetia in prima acquisitione, 1428 primo iulii, confirmatione 1453 et 1517, dalle città di Brescia et Bergamo et i loro territorii confinanti con detta Valle, in maniera che li rettori d'esse non hanno da ingerire in essa, come non hanno quelli di Crema, Verona, Vicenza et altre città, voglia che giurisdittion si sia, vicina o lontana».

¹⁸ «Il Signor Dio et prencipi del mondo et la Natura istessa ha voluto che vi siano le giurisdittioni separate, et perciò detta Sua devotissima Valle non aspetta dalla benignità et carità del Serenissimo suo Prencipe li sia interrotta in parte alcuna detta giurisdittione».

¹⁹ Now Breno, Museo Camuno, Raccolta Putelli, b. 3, fasc. 2.

²⁰ Now Breno, Museo Camuno, Raccolta Putelli, b. 82, fasc. 1.

²¹ *Communitatis Valliscamonicae Statuta*, Brixiae 1498, c. i2r, cap. 278, *De archivio publico fiendo et manutenendo cum tribus clavibus*: «Item statutum est quod de anno praesenti fiat et fieri debeat unum archivium publicum sive armarium in dicta valle cum tribus solariis et tribus seraturis et totidem clavibus, ita quod sine omnibus tribus clavibus nullatenus possit aperiri».

²² Breno, Museo Camuno, Raccolta Putelli, regg. 1-9, 13, 15-16.

²³ P.P. Ormanico, *Considerationi sopra alcune memorie della religione antica dei Camuli, o Camuni, popoli antichi di Valcamonica*, Brescia 1639.

²⁴ Gregorio di Valcamonica, *Curiosi trattenimenti continenti raguagli sacri e profani de' popoli Camuni*, Venice 1698.

²⁵ S. Signaroli, *Brescia 1628: un caso di erudizione politica*, «Aevum», 84 (2010), pp. 761-65.

²⁶ Letter by Domenico Molino to Felice Osio: «Plane constat insignem illum politicum exitisse, et qui singulari prudentiae civilis acumine moderaretur orbem». A. Mussati *Historia Augusta Henrici VII Caesaris*, Venice 1636, p. 71 of the notes by Osio. See S. Signaroli, *L'edizione veneta di Albertino Mussato (1636) e l'erudizione europea di primo Seicento*, «Italia medioevale e umanistica», 50 (2009), pp. 313-41.

²⁷ Certainly, we know that a note, directly or indirectly derived from Henry VII's charter via Bernardino Ronchi and Ottavio Rossi, reached Felice Osio's commentary to the history of Lodi by Otto and Acerbus Morena, in an edition inscribed to Domenico Molino: *Historia rerum Laudensium tempore Federici Aenobarbi Caesaris Othonis Morenae et Acerbi Othonis filii*, ed. by F. Osio, Venice 1629, p. 136. For this point see Signaroli, *La Valle Camonica*, pp. 1103-5.

Abstract

The Commune of Valle Camonica entered the Republic of Venice in 1428. Since then, the capital town of the valley, Breno, kept the institutional archive in a public building, in which the local council of representatives (or parliament) usually met. The archive survived the Commune, that ended its history when the Serenissima died in 1797-1800, and remains among the collections of the Museo Camuno in Breno (managed by the Servizio Archivistico Comprensoriale di Valle Camonica). Existing registers and files allow us to identify many chancellors, active between 1492 and 1797. In particular, documents by Bernardino Ronchi (chancellor since 1586 to 1616) and an inventory, drawn up in the second half of the XVIIth Century, illustrate archival policies and chancery practices in Valle Camonica, and the relations of the Commune with Brescia and Venice. Furthermore, they offer an example of the connection that once linked antiquarian scholarship with political action.

